

An Overview of Inflammation and Potassium in the Oral Cavity

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Abstract:

Potassium is an ion that plays an important role in the body. not only the ion but also ion channels play a role in maintaining body homeostasis. The movement of ions within cells is assisted by ATP and has a role in metabolic activity. Abnormalities in the oral cavity such as periodontal disorders are one of the disorders that are correlated with potassium. Periodontitis is associated with proinflammatory factors such as TNF alpha and IL-6 which turns out to be related to potassium. Apart from that, individuals who lose teeth are related to their potassium intake. Potassium regulates

intracellular organ pH, which is crucial for the enzymatic control of the body's metabolism.

Keywords: *potassium, oral cavity, inflammation.*

Introduction

Potassium is one of ions that can migrate in our membrane cell. Ion channels such as potassium, sodium, chloride, calcium can contribute to homeostasis in our body. The main intracellular electrolytes are phosphate, sulfate, bicarbonate, potassium, and magnesium ions. There are also trace amounts of calcium, chloride, and sodium ions in the cell. These electrolytes contribute in the production and transmission of electrochemical impulses in nerve and muscle cells, as well as reactions essential to the cell's metabolism (Janosik, 2014). Potassium ion (K⁺) transport has previously been identified as an important signature among the metabolic activities of the oral microbiome in periodontitis (Duran-Pinedo et al., 2014). Low potassium intake is positively associated with tooth loss, indicating the beneficial effects of dietary potassium intake on oral health (Kim, & Lee, 2021). Oral cavity has many aspects associated with other organs including hypothalamus and also minerals as micronutrients for the human

body. Saliva secretion is stimulated more by parasympathetic activation and less by sympathetic stimulation. Saliva is low in sodium and high in potassium. It also contains immunoglobulin A (IgA) and compounds that help break down food as well as components that keep the environment in the mouth healthy. Inflammation can occur in other glands including salivary glands for example sialadenitis (Adhikari, 2023).

Potassium can become antibacterial. Antibacterial agents such as lactoperoxidase, glucose oxidase, lactoferrin, lysozyme, and potassium thio- cyanate were included to protect the mucosa and/or teeth from bacterial infection (Kang et al., 2017). In most cases, inflammation is the root cause of physical disorders in vertebrates. The ability of inflammation to transfer fluid across cell layers and membranes, change muscle function, and discomfort is what causes disease. Certain disease processes may be explained by modifications in the amount or functionality of ion channels. Pyelonephritis, allergies, acute lung injury, diarrheal illnesses,

and systemic inflammatory response syndromes, which include septic shock, have all been linked to changes in ion channels. Inflammation-induced pain amply illustrates the critical role that changes in ion transport play in this process. The expression or functionality of these main groups of ion channels are known to be influenced by histamine, ATP, reactive oxygen species, protons generated during inflammation, prostaglandins, leukotrienes, sodium, chloride, potassium, transient receptor potential, and acid-sensing ion channels. Many studies have reported that potassium plays a role in many processes in our cell but the article specific in the

oral cavity was rare. This study will describe the role of potassium especially in inflammation of the oral cavity, and our study focuses on articles which analyze inflammation, potassium and oral cavity.

Result and Discussion

In this study, we found several studies that were obtained by search results on a PubMed search. We found 26 articles (2013-2023) and only 5 articles correlated with inflammation, potassium and oral cavity in their research articles.

Table 1. Study of Inflammation, Potassium and Oral Cavity

Authors	Year	Result
Zhenhui Deng, et al.	2021	The voltage-gated potassium (Kv) 1.3 channel plays a crucial role in the immune and potassium channel inhibitor displaying anti-inflammatory activity ⁽⁶⁾
Minkyung Kang, et al.	2017	Antibacterial agents such as lactoperoxidase, glucose oxidase, lactoferrin, lysozyme, and potassium thiocyanate were included to protect the mucosa and/or teeth from bacterial infection ⁽⁵⁾
Mehran Ajdani, et al.	2022	There no significant difference of salivary pH, calcium, phosphorus, sodium, potassium, albumin, and total protein in celiac disease that this disease one of the chronic inflammation ⁽⁷⁾
Wang, et al.	2017	Potassium channel is a candidate target gene of miR-155-3p in case in periodontitis ⁽⁸⁾
Xin Huang et al.	2015	High extracellular K ⁺ is an inhibitor for NLRP3 inflammasome activation and correlation in oral gingival epithelium ⁽⁹⁾

The active transport system studied in the greatest detail is the sodium–potassium (Na⁺/K⁺)–ATPase pump, and it can move sodium from inside the cell to the extracellular region, the pump also returns potassium to the inside of the cell (Janosik, 2014). Electrolytes with a large charge density have a larger shell of hydration and thus a slower diffusion rate. Na⁺ has a higher charge density than K⁺. Hydrated Na⁺ is therefore larger than hydrated K⁺; hence, the latter tends to move more easily through the membrane. Mitochondria maintain or accumulate cations such as K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺, and Pi. The three electrolytes shown (Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻) cross the bilayer much more slowly than water (Murray, & Davis, 2003). Potassium can be present in various disease disorders. Periodontitis is a prevalent and chronic inflammatory disease and can be

promoted by tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) and other pro-inflammatory cytokines. In this disease potassium channel tetramerization domain containing 1 (Kctd1) was identified as a candidate target gene of miR-155-3p (Liu et al., 2020). Periodontitis correlated with microbiomes in the oral cavity. Potassium ion transport appeared to have a significant role in the pathogenesis process. Potassium levels changed the gingival epithelium's immune response while also making the oral community more pathogenic overall. This study associated with Xin Huang et al., He reported that K⁺ contribute in oral gingival epithelium (Huang et al., 2015). The body's defensive response to infection or stress is known as inflammation, and inflammasomes are molecular platforms that become active in response. This allows pro-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin (IL)-1b

to mature and activate innate immune responses. Nod-like receptor (NLR) and caspase 1-activating cytoplasmic multiprotein complex are the components of inflammasomes (Schroder, & Tschopp, 2010).

As we know we all have microbiomes in our body, especially in the oral cavity. Diabetes, periodontitis, xerostomia is one of the diseases that correlates with accumulation of microbes in the oral cavity. Diabetes is a risk factor for periodontitis, an inflammatory bone disorder and the greatest cause of tooth loss in adults, and diabetes has a significant impact on the gut microbiota (Xiao et al., 2017). According to certain studies, people who are older and have fewer teeth on average consume much more protein, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, and riboflavin on a daily basis. This investigation confirmed the strong correlation between the number of teeth and calcium and potassium intake. Potassium regulates intracellular organ pH, which is crucial for the enzymatic control of the body's metabolism. It also plays a significant role in the acid-base balance, which impacts hormonal action, osteoporosis, aging, and physiological processes related to diet (Kim, & Lee, 2021).

Potassium had a major effect on the expression profiles of the cytokines assessed. The levels of potassium in the periodontal pocket could be an important element of dysbiosis in the oral microbiome. Two cytokines, IL-6 and TNF- α , presented significant differences in their levels of expression associated with the levels of K⁺. Interaction analysis of plaque and K⁺ concentration showed that they indeed had an interacting effect on the values of TNF- α and IL-6 but not in the rest of cytokines values. Changes in the microbiome's functional activities and composition mediate the oral community's dysbiosis. In cases of oral microbiome dysbiosis, K⁺ may be a significant environmental indicator. While inhibiting defense mechanisms like hBD-3 synthesis, which could result in microbial immune subversion, K⁺ also causes the oral microbiota to become more pathogenic (Yost et al., 2017). Within cells, potassium is the most prevalent monovalent ion. Nonetheless, potassium is

found in small amounts in the gingival crevicular fluid in healthy periodontal tissues when it comes into contact with the oral biofilm (Bang et al., 1973).

Periodontitis is associated with endothelial dysfunction, and correlated with calcium activated potassium channels. These findings suggest that endothelial dysfunction is a temporally complex event. Disturbances in endothelial function leading to reduced endothelium-dependent vasodilation are present in patients with cardiovascular risk factors, including hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, diabetes, smoking, aging, atherosclerotic disease, and inflammation. Endothelial-dependent relaxation is impaired by periodontitis, however even in the presence of periodontitis, this impairment is reversible. In ligature animals, the recovery is mediated by the opening of calcium-activated potassium channels in endothelium (Olchanheski et al., 2015). K⁺ is preferentially effluxed to the extracellular medium during physiological conditions via membrane proteins known as K⁺ channels. Two K⁺ channels, known as Kv1.3 and IKCa1, are involved in a variety of processes in osteoclasts and other cells that are frequently found in inflammatory periodontal disease lesions. We first provide an overview of some of the mechanisms by which bone cells, chronically activated/memory T- and B-cells, and macrophages collaborate to initiate bone resorption in periodontal disease and other osteopenic disorders. This will help to clarify the roles played by Kv1.3 and IKCa1 in inflammatory bone resorption. Next, we go over the distinct anatomical characteristics and functions of Kv1.3 and IKCa1 in T-cells, B-cells, macrophages, and osteoclasts in relation to the advancement of periodontal disease (Valverde, Kawai, & Taubman, 2005).

Ion channels have become known as membrane therapeutic targets as well as cancer diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers. The largest and most varied family of ion channels is composed of potassium channels. They have been linked to malignancy and tumor progression in addition to physiological cell proliferation and neoplastic growth. K⁺ channels are membrane proteins that facilitate the selective potassium ion flow

under an electrochemical gradient. Because of this, a large number of these channels have the capacity to cause cancer and have been positively linked to the development of malignancy. Since the TASK family of K⁺ channels has been connected to the etiology and spread of many other malignancies, it was of particular interest. TASK1 (KCNK3 gene), TASK3 (KCNK9 gene), and TASK5 (KCNK15 gene) are members of the TASK family. While TASK1 and TASK3 influence cell excitability and have been linked to a variety of human malignancies, TASK5 is not functionally expressed (Zúñiga et al., 2022). Increased blood pressure and periodontal inflammation are linked to low potassium and low dietary fiber consumption. Furthermore, oxidative stress and chronic inflammation are two ways that periodontitis can increase blood pressure. Consequently, maintaining good dental health is crucial to lowering the risk of HT. Conventional dietary practices that emphasize ingesting more potassium from fruits and vegetables are also likely to lower the risk of periodontitis and HT, two conditions that now worsen older people's quality of life (Yamori et al., 2011).

Conclusion

Homeostasis of the human body is determined by many factors, not only macronutrients but also micronutrients. Ions and ion channels play a role in various metabolic processes. Several disorders or diseases that occur in the oral cavity are related to potassium ions, such as periodontitis which is closely related to potassium intake. Potassium ion (K⁺) transport has previously been identified as an important signature among the metabolic activities of the oral microbiome in periodontitis. Research regarding therapy, disorders and drug development related to potassium can be studied further.

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